

Thermal Dissipation and Heat Management in a Latex Hybrid Mattress: A Quantitative and Visual Analysis Using Advanced Thermal Imaging

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Abstract

Efficient thermal regulation during sleep is critical for ensuring comfort and promoting uninterrupted sleep cycles. This study investigates the thermal dissipation properties of a latex hybrid mattress composed of a 50mm layer of 80D natural latex, a 50mm layer of 30D soft polyurethane (PU) foam, and a 100mm base of 32D high-resilience PU foam. The mattress, encased in 450 GSM polyester fabric featuring a textured profile designed to enhance breathability, was subjected to simulated body heat at 37°C. Thermal imaging, performed using the Fluke TC01A thermal camera, recorded temperature decay over five intervals (0, 6, 13, 46, and 100 seconds) as the mattress returned to ambient temperature (31.9°C). The analysis revealed rapid heat dissipation during the initial 13 seconds, followed by a gradual cooling phase. A second-order polynomial regression was applied to model the cooling behavior, providing a precise mathematical representation of the temperature decline. These findings demonstrate the mattress's effectiveness in managing thermal loads, making it suitable for improving sleep comfort, particularly in warmer climates.

1. Introduction

Temperature regulation during sleep is a key factor in ensuring optimal sleep quality. Poor thermal management by mattresses can lead to overheating, which disrupts sleep stages and reduces restorative deep sleep. Research shows that materials with better breathability and faster heat dissipation capabilities are preferable for maintaining ideal sleeping conditions. Latex and polyurethane foams, frequently used in mattress design, offer diverse properties that influence both support and thermal regulation.

This study investigates the thermal dissipation properties of a latex hybrid mattress, which combines the breathability of natural latex with the support of PU foams. Using advanced thermal imaging, we quantify the mattress's heat dissipation capabilities after exposure to a heat source simulating body temperature. By integrating statistical analysis and a regression model, we provide a comprehensive assessment of the cooling behavior of this mattress.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Mattress Construction

The latex hybrid mattress used in this study consists of the following layers:

- Top Layer: 50mm of 80D natural latex.
- Middle Layer: 50mm of 30D soft PU foam.
- Base Layer: 100mm of high-resilience PU foam.

The mattress is encased in a 450 GSM polyester fabric with a textured design, specifically engineered to enhance airflow and heat dissipation across the mattress surface.

2.2 Thermal Imaging Equipment

The thermal imaging data was captured using the Fluke TC01A thermal camera, equipped with:

- Resolution: 256x192 pixels for high-definition thermal imaging.
- Frame Rate: 25 Hz for smooth video capture.

- Temperature Sensitivity: 50 mK (0.05°C), enabling detection of fine temperature differences.
- Accuracy: $\pm 2\%$ or $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, ensuring reliable measurements across a broad temperature range.

2.3 Experimental Procedure

A heat source at 37°C, replicating human body temperature, was applied to the mattress surface for 2 minutes. Upon removal of the heat source, thermal images were captured at intervals of 0, 6, 13, 46, and 100 seconds. The initial ambient temperature of the mattress surface was 31.9°C. Thermal dissipation data were recorded and visualized through heat maps to assess the mattress's cooling performance.

3. Results

3.1 Temperature Decay and Cooling Rate

The cooling behavior of the mattress was recorded at each time interval after the heat source was removed. These intervals represent the time between each recorded temperature measurement and were calculated as the difference between consecutive time points: 0 seconds, 6 seconds, 13 seconds, 46 seconds, and 100 seconds.

The time intervals were computed as follows:

- **First interval:** $6-0=6$ seconds
- **Second interval:** $13-6=7$ seconds
- **Third interval:** $46-13=33$ seconds
- **Fourth interval:** $100-46=54$ seconds

These intervals indicate the duration over which the temperature change occurred. The rate of cooling ($^\circ\text{C}/\text{s}$) was calculated by dividing the temperature change during each interval by the corresponding time interval.

Table 1: Temperature Decay and Rate of Cooling

Time Interval (s)	Temperature Change (°C)	Rate of Cooling (°C/s)
6	-1.9	-0.3167
7	-0.7	-0.1000
33	-0.9	-0.0273
54	-0.8	-0.0148

This table illustrates the observed temperature changes and the corresponding cooling rates. The highest rate of cooling was observed during the first 6 seconds, when the surface temperature dropped by 1.9°C. As the temperature approached ambient conditions, the rate of cooling decelerated.

3.2 Cooling Curve Regression Analysis

To better understand the cooling dynamics, a second-order polynomial regression was applied to the temperature-time data:

$$T(t) = 6.12 \times 10^{-4} \cdot t^2 - 0.095 \cdot t + 35.37$$

Where: $T(t)$ is the surface temperature in °C at time t in seconds.

This quadratic model closely matches the observed cooling behavior, with a rapid temperature drop in the early phase, followed by gradual stabilization as the mattress returns to ambient temperature..

Regression Fit Coefficients:

- **a** (quadratic term): 6.12×10^{-4}
- **b** (linear term): -0.095
- **c** (constant): 35.37

The cooling curve generated by this model is illustrated in the graph below. The fitted curve closely follows the observed data, indicating that the cooling process can be accurately represented by a quadratic function over the time intervals observed.

3.3 Heat Map Visualization

Thermal imaging heat maps captured at each interval visually demonstrate the cooling process:

- Figure 1: T = 0 seconds - The mattress surface temperature is 36.2°C immediately after heat source removal.

- Figure 2: T = 6 seconds - The temperature drops to 34.3°C, with rapid heat dissipation evident at the surface edges.

- Figure 3: T = 13 seconds - The temperature decreases further to 33.6°C. Heat is more evenly distributed across the mattress surface.

- Figure 4: T = 46 seconds - The temperature reaches 32.7°C, with residual warmth observed primarily in the central region.

- Figure 5: T = 100 seconds - The temperature stabilizes at 31.9°C, returning to ambient conditions, indicating complete dissipation of the applied heat.

4. Discussion

4.1 Thermal Management and Cooling Mechanisms

The rapid decrease in temperature during the first 13 seconds highlights the effectiveness of the latex hybrid mattress in dissipating heat. The breathable latex layer, combined with the textured polyester cover, allows for efficient airflow across the surface, facilitating rapid heat loss.

4.2 Implications for Sleep Comfort

The results suggest that the latex hybrid mattress is well-suited for environments where thermal regulation is essential, such as warm climates or for individuals prone to overheating during sleep. By dissipating heat quickly, the mattress minimizes the risk of thermal discomfort.

4.3 Comparative Performance

Compared to memory foam mattresses, which tend to retain heat for extended periods, the latex hybrid structure demonstrates superior thermal management properties.

4.4 Statistical Results

The statistical analysis provides quantitative evidence of the mattress's heat dissipation properties. The rate of cooling, which is highest immediately after heat source removal, aligns with the observed behaviour of latex and foam hybrid structures, which allow for quick initial heat release due to their breathability and material properties. As the temperature approaches ambient conditions, the rate of cooling slows significantly, indicative of the mattress reaching thermal equilibrium.

The quadratic regression model further supports these findings by providing a mathematical description of the cooling process. The high initial rate of temperature change underscores the mattress's effectiveness in dissipating heat, particularly during the critical early moments after heat source removal, which is essential for maintaining sleep comfort in real-world applications.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that latex hybrid mattresses, particularly when paired with breathable fabrics, offer superior thermal dissipation properties. The rapid cooling observed in the first 13 seconds after heat exposure underscores the mattress's effectiveness in managing body heat. The findings suggest that such mattresses are ideal for individuals seeking enhanced thermal comfort during sleep.

6. Acknowledgments

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7. References

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